

FACTORS SHAPING TEACHING COMPETENCE AMONG NOVICE EARLY CHILDHOOD TEACHERS

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ABSTRACT

Teaching competence of early childhood education (ECE) teachers is essential because it empowers them to deliver effective and meaningful learning experiences that foster young learners' academic growth and holistic development. This study explored the factors shaping teaching competence among novice early childhood teachers, focusing on work-life balance, pre-service training, and knowledge of child development. Using a descriptive–correlational design, data were gathered from a purposive sample of newly hired early childhood teachers in selected schools within Lanao del Norte, Philippines. The data revealed that the participants assessed their work-life balance and the quality of their pre-service training as generally high, while their knowledge of child development was outstanding. Work–life balance and pre-service training significantly influenced teaching competence, whereas knowledge of child development demonstrated no significant influence. Although understanding child development remains foundational, its impact on actual classroom practice may rely on experiential learning and contextual supports such as institutional guidance and mentoring. Future studies may explore how continuous professional development, coaching, and sustained mentoring mediate the relationship between personal and professional factors in shaping teaching competence, particularly among novice early childhood educators.

Keywords: *Teaching competence, novice teachers, early childhood education, work-life balance, pre-service training, knowledge of child development*

INTRODUCTION

The early years of education play a crucial role in shaping children's lifelong learning, and thus, the competence of early childhood teachers directly affects educational quality. Novice teachers, however, often face multiple challenges as they transition from theory to practice. They navigate new learning environments, manage diverse learners, and balance personal responsibilities, all of which can influence their teaching effectiveness. As the Philippine education landscape continues to evolve, understanding the factors that shape teaching competence among beginning early childhood educators becomes essential for improving teacher preparation and retention. This study aimed to identify the factors shaping teaching competence among novice early childhood teachers. Specifically, it sought to: determine the levels of work-life balance, their assessment on the quality of pre-service training, knowledge of child development, and teaching competence; and identify which factors significantly influence teaching competence.

This study is anchored on Albert Bandura's Social Cognitive Theory (1986), which emphasizes that learning and competence develop through the interaction of personal factors, behavior, and environment. Teachers acquire and refine their teaching competence through observational learning, self-efficacy, and reciprocal interactions with their professional contexts. For novice early childhood teachers, competence emerges as they apply knowledge gained from pre-service training, build confidence through experience, and balance personal and work demands. Thus, teaching competence is shaped not only by individual capability but also by the social and environmental conditions that support professional growth and continuous learning.

Maintaining a healthy work-life balance is not just a personal objective for early childhood educators; it is closely linked to the caliber of care and education they offer young children. As a result, work-life balance becomes a critical area of focus, particularly for new early childhood educators who are still figuring out who they are as professionals, adjusting to institutional expectations, and learning how to draw boundaries between their personal and professional lives (Karatepe 2023).

Before assuming full responsibility for a class, aspiring teachers are exposed to classroom management, lesson planning, and instructional strategies through their pre-service training. It introduces aspiring teachers to core professional practices—classroom management, lesson planning, and instructional strategies—through coursework, case-based learning, and supervised practicum, giving them structured opportunities to apply theory to classroom situations; empirical studies of pre-service cohorts report that these program components are central to developing classroom management competence and instructional preparedness before teachers assume full responsibility for a class (Junker et. al., 2021; Basalo & Salvador, 2022).

In early childhood settings—where children's behaviors, abilities, and responses differ markedly by developmental stage—novice teachers' understanding of child development is critical for effective practice; recent empirical work demonstrates that

strengthening teachers' developmental and pedagogical knowledge improves classroom interaction quality, assessment practices, and the use of developmentally appropriate strategies to support children's cognitive and social learning (Siraj et al., 2023; Pyle et al., 2022). This information becomes a crucial tool for novice teachers to use when making decisions in the classroom that support their emotional and intellectual development.

Teaching competence of early childhood education (ECE) teachers is essential because it empowers them to deliver effective and meaningful learning experiences that foster young learners' academic growth and holistic development. Teachers in this field frequently work in demanding environments characterized by high emotional expectations, role ambiguity, and the constant need to adapt. This is especially true for recently hired or inexperienced early childhood educators. Iannone (2020) highlighted that because of their significant impact on future generations, their competence and capacity to manage personal and professional obligations are crucial for both their own success and well-being as well as the general efficacy of early childhood education.

Research Questions

1. What are the participants' self-reports of their work-life balance?
2. What is the participants' assessment of the quality of their pre-service training?
3. What is the participants' knowledge level of child development in terms of:
 - 3.1. Motor Development (Fine);
 - 3.2. Cognitive Development; and
 - 3.3. Social and Emotional Development?
4. What is the participants' level of teaching competence?
5. Do the participants' work-life balance, pre-service training, and knowledge of child development significantly influence their teaching competence?

METHODOLOGY

This study employed a descriptive–correlational research design, which allowed the identification of relationships among variables and the determination of which factors influence teaching competence among novice early childhood teachers. The participants were 62 novice early childhood teachers with 1–2 years of teaching experience from the public schools of Lanao del Norte. A purposive sampling technique was used to ensure that the participants represented teachers who were in the early stages of their teaching careers.

A Likert Scale was used as the research instrument in the study. The researcher modified the items from Fisher et al. (2003) to assess the participants' work-life balance. Meanwhile, the assessment of the participants' pre-service training was based on Darling-Hammond's (2006) tool, and knowledge of child development items was based on Ilar and Mendoza's (2025) study. To assess the teaching competence of the novice early childhood teachers, it was adapted from Tschannen-Moran & Woolfolk Hoy (2001). The instruments underwent content validation by the panel members and experts in the field,

and were subjected to reliability testing. Cronbach's alpha was utilized to determine the internal consistency of the instrument. As suggested by Tavakol and Dennick (2011), a reliability coefficient of 0.70 and above is generally deemed acceptable, whereas higher values reflect greater internal consistency.

The study adhered to ethical standards for human research. Participants were informed about the study's purpose, the confidentiality of their responses, and their right to withdraw at any point. Informed consent was obtained before data collection. As to statistical tools that were employed, data were analyzed using descriptive statistics such as frequency, percentage, mean, and standard deviation, and multiple regression analysis to determine predictive factors influencing teaching competence.

RESULTS

Research Question 1. *What are the participants' self-reports of work-life balance?*

Table 1

Descriptive Statistics of the Participants' Self-Reports of Work-Life Balance

Score Range	Description	Interpretation	Frequency	Percentage
4.51 – 5.00	Strongly Agree	Very high	5	8.06
3.51 – 4.50	Agree	High	28	45.16
2.51 – 3.50	Neutral	Moderate	27	43.55
1.51 – 2.50	Disagree	Low	2	3.23
1.00 – 1.50	Strongly Disagree	Very low	0	0.00
Total			62	100
Mean				3.60
Interpretation				High
SD				0.57

Research Question 2. *What is the participants' assessment of the quality of their pre-service training?*

Table 2

Descriptive Statistics of the Participants' Assessment of the Quality of their Pre-Service Teaching

Score Range	Description	Interpretation	Frequency	Percentage
4.51 – 5.00	Strongly Agree	Very high	37	59.68
3.51 – 4.50	Agree	High	24	38.71
2.51 – 3.50	Neutral	Moderate	1	1.61
1.51 – 2.50	Disagree	Low	0	0.00
1.00 – 1.50	Strongly Disagree	Very low	0	0.00

Total	62	100
Mean		4.61
Interpretation		Very high
SD		0.48

Research Question 3. *What is the participants' knowledge level of child development in terms of: Cognitive, Fine Motor, and Socio-Emotional?*

Table 3
Summary Table of the Participants' Knowledge of Child Development

Indicators	Mean	SD	Interpretation
Fine Motor Development	8.87	2.06	Outstanding
Cognitive Development	8.48	2.63	Outstanding
Socio-Emotional Development	8.85	2.41	Outstanding
Composite Mean	8.73	2.37	Outstanding

Research Question 4. *What is the participants' level of teaching competence?*

Table 4
Descriptive Statistics of the Participants' Level of Teaching Competence

Score Range	Description	Interpretation	Frequency	Percentage
4.51 – 5.00	Strongly Agree	Outstanding	39	62.90
3.51 – 4.50	Agree	Very Good	21	33.87
2.51 – 3.50	Neutral	Good	2	3.23
1.51 – 2.50	Disagree	Fair	0	0.00
1.00 – 1.50	Strongly Disagree	Poor	0	0.00
Total			62	100
Mean			4.57	
Interpretation			Outstanding	
SD			0.43	

Research Question 5. *Do the participants' work-life balance, pre-service training, and knowledge of child development significantly influence their teaching competence?*

H₀₁: The participants' work-life balance, pre-service training, and knowledge of child development do not significantly influence their teaching competence.

H₀₂: The participants' work-life balance does not significantly influence their teaching competence.

H₀₃: The participants' assessment of the quality of their pre-service training does not significantly influence their teaching competence.

H₀₄: The participants' knowledge of child development does not significantly influence their teaching competence.

Table 5
Multiple Regression Analysis on the Predictors of Teaching Competence

Predictor	Unstand ardized Beta	SE	Standardize d β	95% CI		t	p
				Lower	Upper		
Constant	0.934	0.350				2.667	0.010
Work-life Balance	0.145	0.058	0.189	0.036	0.343	2.476*	0.016
Pre-service Training	0.679	0.069	0.750	0.596	0.904	9.765**	<.001
Knowledge of Child Development	-0.002	0.015	-0.012	-0.154	0.131	-0.164	0.131

Model Summary			
R = 0.841	R ² = 0.708	Adjusted R ² = 0.693	F (3,58) = 46.8
p <.001			

Model Equation: TP = 0.145WLB + 0.679PST + 0.934

DISCUSSION

Research Question 1: Table 1

Table 1 shows the participants' self-reports of their work-life balance. The figures reveal that the participants assessed their work-life balance as generally *high*, as indicated in the overall mean of 3.60, which suggests that, despite they are novices in the profession, they can manage the balance between their professional responsibilities and personal life. From the distribution, it can be gleaned that 28 or 45.16 percent of them rated that they have a *high* work-life balance, while 27 or 43.55 percent rated as having a *moderate* work-life balance.

Research Question 2: Table 2

Table 2 shows the participants' assessment of the quality of their pre-service training. The results indicate that they rated the quality of their pre-service training as *very high*, with an overall mean of 4.61 and a standard deviation of 0.48. This suggests that the participants viewed their pre-service programs as effective in providing them with the essential knowledge, skills, and experiences needed for the teaching profession. From the distribution, it can be observed that 37 or 59.68 percent of the participants rated their

pre-service training as *very high*, while 24 or 38.71 percent rated it as *high*, suggesting that the majority of novice teachers experienced comprehensive and well-structured training before entering the profession.

Research Question 3: Table 3

Table 3 presents a summary of the participants' knowledge of child development. The results show that all three domains—Fine Motor Development ($M = 8.87$), Cognitive Development ($M = 8.48$), and Socio-Emotional Development ($M = 8.85$)—were rated as *Outstanding*. The composite mean of 8.73 further indicates that novice early childhood teachers have a strong and well-rounded understanding of developmental milestones across the motor, cognitive, and socio-emotional domains.

Research Question 4: Table 4

Table 4 presents the descriptive statistics of the participants' level of teaching competence. It can be gleaned from the figures that the participants' overall level of teaching competence is *Outstanding*, as reflected by the mean score of 4.57 ($SD = 0.43$). This result implies that the novice early childhood teachers generally perceive themselves as competent in performing their teaching responsibilities. In addition, the results indicate that the novice early childhood educators can motivate their students to actively participate in the classroom and as well as design their teaching strategies for them to be actively engaged in the teaching-learning process. The results show that the majority (62.90%) of them rated their teaching competence as *outstanding*, while 21 or 33.87% of them rated it as *very good*. This finding supports Darling-Hammond's (2021) assertion that teachers' competence is strongly linked to their ability to apply effective teaching strategies, manage classrooms, and integrate learner-centered approaches that promote meaningful learning.

Research Question 5: Table 5

Table 5 shows the multiple regression results that examined the influence of Work-Life Balance, Pre-service Training, and Knowledge of Child Development on Teaching Performance. The regression model is significant, $F(3, 58) = 46.80$, $p < .001$. In this study, there is sufficient evidence that the combination of the participants' work-life balance, their pre-service training, and their knowledge of child development significantly influences their teaching competence. Therefore, the first null hypothesis can be rejected. There is sufficient evidence that the combination of work-life balance, pre-service training, and knowledge of child development significantly influences their teaching competence. The predictors explained 69.3% of the variance in teaching performance (Adjusted $R^2 = 0.693$). The remaining 31.7% may be attributed to mentoring and coaching by their direct supervisor. The model equation was $TP = 0.145WLB + 0.679PST + 0.934$, with variables Teaching Performance (TP), Work-life Balance (WLB), and Pre-service Training (PST).

This result supports the findings of Obispo (2023), who noted that well-designed teacher education programs—particularly those that integrate both theoretical and

practical components—significantly shape the pedagogical competence of beginning teachers. Likewise, Acarli and Kasap (2021) emphasized that the quality of pre-service training directly influences professional, methodological, and social competencies, which are foundational to effective teaching performance. These results affirm that robust pre-service preparation plays a critical role in equipping novice teachers with the pedagogical skills and confidence necessary to perform effectively in real classroom settings.

Taken singly, work-life balance also showed a significant influence on teaching competence ($t= 2.476$, $p = 0.016$). Therefore, the second null hypothesis stating that work-life balance does not significantly influence teaching competence is rejected. This means that those who had a better work-life balance tended to have better teaching performance.

Meanwhile, it can be gleaned from the figures that for every point increase in the work-life balance, there is a corresponding .145 increase in teaching competence. This finding is consistent with the study of Yburan and Tantiado (2025), who found that work-life balance significantly influences teaching competence among teachers in Cagayan de Oro City. Similarly, Burić & Kim (2021) emphasized that teachers who effectively manage their workload and personal well-being exhibit improved performance and professional efficacy. These results affirm that teachers who maintain a balanced relationship between their professional responsibilities and personal life tend to demonstrate higher teaching competence.

Moreover, the participants' assessment of the quality of their pre-service training also showed a significant influence on teaching competence ($t=9.765$, $p=.001$). Hence, the third null hypothesis stating that the quality of pre-service training does not significantly influence teaching competence is rejected. Further, it can be gleaned from the figures that for every point increase in the pre-service training, there is a corresponding 0.679 increase in teaching competence. This finding implies that teachers who have undergone more structured and comprehensive pre-service training tend to exhibit stronger teaching competence in classroom management, instructional delivery, and learner engagement. Large-scale meta-analytic evidence shows that teacher training programs produce meaningful gains in teachers' knowledge and practical skills, with pre-service programs that combine strong knowledge building and guided field experiences demonstrating particularly robust effects on teacher competence (Zhang et. al., 2024).

However, there is no substantial data that would support the assumption that knowledge has a significant influence ($\beta = -0.012$, $p = .131$) on teaching competence; therefore, the fourth null hypothesis is not rejected. From the findings of this study, while conceptual understanding of child development is essential, it may not automatically manifest in observable teaching behaviors unless supported by opportunities for application, guided practice, and contextual experience. Knowledge may remain theoretical when not reinforced by real classroom situations, structured mentoring, or hands-on instructional support. This finding highlights the distinction between what teachers know and what they can do in practice, underscoring the importance of experiential learning, reflective practice, and ongoing professional development in the

development of teaching competence. This finding aligns with the results of Pažur et. al. (2024), who emphasized that although early childhood educators may demonstrate a solid understanding of developmental principles, such knowledge alone does not directly translate into higher teaching competence. Instead, teaching competence is often strengthened through reflective practice, mentorship, and contextual experience. Similarly, Kurrle et al. (2025) noted that professional skills in early childhood education are developed through continuous interaction with learners and real-world classroom situations, rather than being solely based on theoretical knowledge.

Conclusions

1. Generally, the participants reported a high level of work-life balance. This indicates that novice early childhood teachers are able to maintain a reasonable equilibrium between their professional and personal responsibilities.
2. The participants rated their pre-service training as generally very high, implying that they perceive the quality of their teacher preparation programs as highly effective in equipping them with essential knowledge and pedagogical skills.
3. Overall, the participants' knowledge of child development was outstanding. These results indicate that novice early childhood teachers possess a broad and adequate grasp of developmental milestones across the motor, cognitive, and socio-emotional domains.
4. The teaching competence of the participants was rated as outstanding, suggesting that novice teachers demonstrate a strong ability to utilize interactive strategies and technological tools in classroom instruction.
5. Taken as a whole, work-life balance, pre-service training, and knowledge of child development significantly influence teaching competence, confirming that both personal and professional factors contribute to how novice teachers perform in the classroom.

Recommendations

It is recommended that: Educational Institutions and Teacher Training Providers may strengthen pre-service programs by expanding field-based experiences across diverse early childhood settings, reinforcing reflective practice through structured journaling and guided conferences, and improving competency-based assessments to ensure consistent mastery of child development and teaching strategies; School Administrators are encouraged to sustain and enhance the high levels of work-life balance and teaching competence by maintaining reasonable teaching loads, ensuring fair distribution of tasks, and supporting teacher wellness through mental health and professional development programs; and Future Researchers may consider expanding the scope of this study by including a larger and more diverse sample of novice early childhood teachers from various regions to enhance the generalizability of the findings.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

The researcher affirms that the study was conducted in full compliance with established ethical guidelines. Informed consent was obtained from all participants, who were clearly informed of their voluntary participation and their right to withdraw from the study at any time without penalty. Anonymity and confidentiality were strictly maintained, and all procedures adhered to the provisions of the Data Privacy Act to ensure the protection of participants' personal information. The well-being of respondents was given utmost priority throughout the research process, and no psychological, social, or professional risks were imposed. The researcher declares that no conflict of interest exists in the conduct of this study and that plagiarism was strictly avoided through proper citation and original analysis. All findings were interpreted objectively, without bias, and were used solely for academic and research purposes. The researcher also acknowledges that artificial intelligence tools were used only to assist in writing refinement and organization, with all substantive ideas, interpretations, and conclusions remaining the researcher's own for full transparency and disclosure.

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